

Impact of Abusive Supervision on Emotional Exhaustion, Counterproductive Work Behaviours and Intention to Quit: Moderating Role of Emotional Intelligence

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 09, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Leader-member Exchange Theory (LMX), Abusive supervision (AS), Intention to quit (ITQ), Social Exchange Theory (SET), Emotional Intelligence (EI), Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWB), Emotional Exhaustion (EE).</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5172958</p>	<p><i>Current study has been conducted to examine the inherent mechanism of abusive behavior of supervisors and its effects based on Leader Member and Social Exchange Theories. The interactions among abusive leadership and counterproductive work behaviors, intent to leave a job, and emotional exhaustion with the moderating influence of emotional intelligence have been investigated. The information were gathered from 472 people employed in banks of Punjab, Pakistan. The research used SPSS 22 and AMOS 24 to analyze the information and conduct statistical analysis. Findings from this research show that abusive supervision has a positive correlation with emotional exhaustion of employees, their behaviors that are contrary to the values of the organization and their plan to leave the organization while emotional intelligence did not act as a moderator with the concerned variables in this study. Literature, however, has shown that emotional intelligence is a valuable source for workers to transcend the negative effects of abuse. The current study concludes that firms need to understand the damaging impacts of the abusive behavior of managers and must try to prevent such behaviors by implementing ethical leadership and devising HR policies to support the subordinates, reduce stressful situations and maltreatments among employees.</i></p>

Introduction

According to Kelloway & Barling (2010), management has the ability to affect other people's actions in a manner that they function more proficiently. Leaders can have a significant influence on a team or group for the accomplishment of organizational goals (Judge & Piccolo, 2004). The joint objective and a common goal helps the group to set direction but leadership is the mechanism that paves the way to achieve those goals and hence heading towards success (Northouse, 2018; Ciulla, 1999). The way a leader offers guidance, distributes the workload of the team and administers problems that arise daily has a significant effect on followers' behavior (Schmid, Peus, & PircherVerdorfer, 2018). The combination of support and ethics is therefore essential to maintain workers' safety when performing leadership. Leaders should involve employees, provide them the feedback, share their expectations, and foster creative solutions for problems (Northouse, 2018; ForsBrandebö, Österberg, & Berglund, 2019). Self-actualization, honesty, and authenticity constitute the favorable behaviors of leaders. On the contrary, unfavorable conduct involves deviations from the workplace, dishonesty, coercive supervision, misconduct, malpractices and self-centeredness (Paulhus & Williams, 2002). So far, many scholars have been discussing favorable leadership behaviors, but very few studies have been undertaken on adverse leadership elements. In this direction, the present research is bringing an attention. Although Robinson and Bennett (1995) have been more attentive to poisonous, counterproductive and deviant behaviors over the past few centuries, most of them have been aimed towards subordinates or junior staff (Tepper et al., 2006), but a little research has stressed the dark side of managers and leaders (Tepper et al., 2001). Counterproductive behaviors at job, mental fatigue, and the turnover intention are few results generated by abusive supervisory behavior mentioned in this article. However, researchers have explored direct correspondence among these, but moderator tends to undermine these interactions (Tepper et al., 2001).

Jena and Pradhan (2016) have identified various moderating variables, including emotional intelligence, which can minimize the intention of staff to leave due to abusive behavior. Present study brings novelty by examining the moderating effect of emotional intelligence between relationships i.e. abusive supervision & emotional

exhaustion and abusive supervision & counterproductive work behaviors. This research attracts the attention of the researcher in this manner. For this paper, two theories (LMX and SET), based on mutual relationship have been used (Blau, 1964). The theories under debate are about fair exchange of relationships and are more relevant in summarizing the effects of leadership behavior on the duties of subordinates (Cropanzano, Howes, Grandey, & Toth, 1997).

1.1 Research Objectives

This study sought to examine the relationship between AS and its repercussions, i.e. EE, CWB, ITQ, as well as to examine emotional intelligence's moderating role in all these connections. This study therefore sets out the research objectives below;

- To examine the relationship between AS and EE
- To investigate the relationship between AS and CWB
- To examine the relationship between AS and ITQ
- To investigate the moderating effect of EI among said relationships

Theoretical Underpinning

Leader Member Exchange (LMX) Theory

LMX theory is very much associated with relationships of managers with their employees. A healthy connection depends on love, allegiance, respect and trust according to this theory (Maslyn and Liden, 1998). As stated by Graen and Liden (1980) previous results from the LMX theory indicate that there are differential relationships between people heading subordinates and working group members. The theory has received attention since several years from many scientists and the theory has been used in 600 journal papers, figure reported as of December 2013. Leaders provide their staff with mentoring, support and many other development possibilities in high-quality relationships. Thus, in case of high-quality connections, valued services are then shared. When employees think they earn valuable tangible and intangible benefits, they seek to reciprocate their supervisors with favorable work behavior (Gouldner, 1960). On the other hand, reacting to the manager in a high-quality relationship takes a negative form where the employee or the subordinate expects to receive a favorable treatment from the employer but gets unfavorable; rather than mutually advantageous, thereby getting a negative gesture.

Social Exchange Theory (SET)

The Social Exchange Theory was launched by Homans in 1958. While different theorists have different opinions on that theory, the majority of views converge on a stage where social interactions lead to commitments (Emerson, 1976). Economic exchanges are very evident and the behaviors of the job are defined explicitly. Social exchanges, on the other side, are informal and are not explicitly defined (Rousseau, 1989; Middlemiss, 2011). Those are generally based on expectations and oral promises (Rousseau, 1995, 1989). Therefore, as per Rousseau (1989), this informal arrangement is commonly referred to as a psychological contract. Reciprocity is this psychological contract's binding mechanism. If someone, in a relationship, offers something positive or negative to the other individual, the other person reciprocates in the same way recognizing his duty Uhl-Bien & Maslyn (2003); Gouldner, (1960) hence balancing the exchange relationship.

Hypotheses development

Emotional exhaustion occurs in different forms such as psychological strain, physical exhaustion, excessive stress and depletion of psychological and emotional resources (Wright & Cropanzano, 1998). According to Maslach et al., (2001) he / she becomes emotionally exhausted when the interpersonal interactions of an individual do not prove satisfactory to him / her. The individual who works under pressure will experience mental fatigue and low energy, while the psychological stress will occur because of resource depletion. The resulting emotional exhaustion reduces the ability of a person to confront and satisfy emotional requirements on the job (Nikolova et al, 2019).

Since abusive managers are not interested in their interactions with supporters, they engage in manipulative policies leaving an adverse and unethical effect on the perception of staff and their subordinates perceive them and organizations as a whole in a suspicious way thereby becoming emotionally drained and engaged in deviant behaviors (Gkorezis, 2015). Abusive monitoring is also closely linked with tension and mental tightness, which is the origin of burnout and subsequently leads to emotional exhaustion. It is also apparent that increased thoughts of coercive control contribute to high levels of depression, mental discontentment, anger and anxiety (Ashforth, 1994). Abusive supervision is responsible for the mental distress of the workforce and eventually makes workers indulge in counterproductive work behaviors (Zhang et al, 2019). Those who work directly under the abusive manager exhibit elevated stress rates and low energy in their job environment (Ashforth, 1994). Whitman et al. (2014) have disclosed the positive link of emotional fatigue with abusive supervision. Therefore it is hypothesized on the grounds of the above literature;

H1: A positive and significant relationship exists between AS and EE.

It has been researched that participants react to their managers in the same manner they were treated by them in perspective of SET and LMX. For example, when they find their bosses to be trustworthy, they seek to do even more work to be superior in their employments (Mossholder, Yang, & Peng, 2009). To the contrary, workers who do not find their management to be trustworthy and assume them unethical, tend to engage in deceitful and

deviant behaviors such as not working hard, stealing the organizational stuff, revealing private data, deliberately working slowly, etc. (Bruk-Lee et al., 2009). Research has shown that people with bad work experiences including aggression, drainage and mental fatigue are more likely to engage in retaliatory behaviors (Dutton, E. Fox, Bowles, & Russo, 2001). This also concludes that deviant behaviors at the organizational level are more prevalent (Miller, Marcus-Newhall, Carlson, & Pedersen, 2000). This might include misuse of official possessions by taking them at home and speaking badly about firm in their circle (Ahmad & Asghar 2017). Quite evidently, workers usually exhibit deviant behaviors to coworkers because the supervisor is difficult to deviate or they are afraid of punishment or retaliation (Ahmad & Asghar, 2017). Previous research indicates that abused subordinates would seek retaliation by adopting counterproductive work behaviors in response to abusive supervision (Kim et al., 2018). A further research has shown that abusive management is consistent with the interpersonal and organizational deviance of employees (Sia & Hussain 2017). Thus, with the assistance of empirical research, personal involvement in counterproductive and retaliated behaviors has been discovered underneath a deviant setting (Inness et al., 2005). It is suggested on the grounds of the above arguments;

H2: A positive and significant relationship exists between AS and CWB.

An employee's intention to deliberately withdraw from the company is known as turnover intention (Mobley et al., 1978; Mobley, 1977). Turnover has some costs associated with it including training cost, cost of hiring etc. Role ambiguities, vague position at workplace, and job disputes are main causes of mental stress (Boles, 2004). High level of commitment is associated with high levels of satisfaction of employees with their work and thus satisfied employees have reduced plans to leave the organization (Beehr & Raabe, 2003). Research on abusive supervisory behavior indicates that abusive practices have resulted in a lack of happiness, commitment, faithfulness, honesty and truth among employees (Hamid et al., 2015). Turnover theories indicated that unsatisfied staff looks for alternates, resulting in staff turnover (Spector, 1997).

Stress caused by supervisor's abuse is an immediate predictor of employees' turnover, leading to mental strain, which ultimately reduces employees' morale and leads to increased absenteeism and turnover (Schwepker Jr, 2001; Valentine & Barnett, 2003; Mulki, Locander, & Jaramillo, 2006). The statement is also backed by LMX and SET theories that coercive monitoring is directly related to employees' desire to leave due to the pressure it creates, thus involving staff in counterproductive job behaviors and eventually reducing their job efficiency (O'Boyle Jr et al., 2012). Thereby, the goals of the organization are compromised in this whole situation. So it's hypothesized on the grounds of the above literature;

H3: Direct and significant relationship exists between AS and ITQ.

Formerly, an intelligence quotient (IQ) was one of the supreme variables of one's professional achievement but the idea was revised with the origination of Emotional Quotient (EQ). Salovey and Mayer (1990) first launched the word emotional quotient and described it as;

“An ability to recognize the meanings of emotions and their relationships and to reason and problem-solve on the basis of them. Emotional intelligence is involved in the capacity to perceive emotions, assimilate emotion-related feelings, understand the information of these emotions, and manage them” (p. 267).

As specified by Schaufeli & Enzmann (1998); Maslach & Goldberg (1998), the word burnout is defined as a long-lasting stress state that generally arises due to unchallenging and unrewarding assignments or bad feedback and absence of acceptance (Maslach, 1982). Since emotional fatigue is also a burnout component (Maslach & Jackson 1986), therefore it is suggested that emotional fatigue has negative impacts on the physical and mental health of staff and therefore on the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization. Subordinates working on high demands for jobs require substantial resources to complete tasks (Van Hooftegem & De Witte, 2019). The attempt to transfer resources to subordinates from violence would increase emotional fatigue and contribute to the CWB, according to Conservation of Resources theory (COR) (Liu & Yu, 2019). Research suggests that if workers have better resources, they react differently to abusive management – with fewer negative results (Ahmad et al., 2019).

It is because individuals who are emotionally intelligent find opportunity in every situation, instead of taking it as a challenge and do their best to cope with them. Thus emotional exhaustion and emotional intelligence have opposite association Mikolajczak et al. (2007), which implies that people with high emotional intelligence have less emotional exhaustion rather than those with little emotional intelligence. As stated by Ashforth (1994) that workers suffer from mental exhaustion in stressful environments induced by abusive supervision. But emotionally smart employees are less emotionally exhausted and can deal with mental stress. So it is hypothesized on the grounds of the above statements that;

H4: The relationship between AS and EE is moderated by EI such that lower the EI stronger will be the relationship and vice versa.

Employees are engaged in deviant job behaviors at both person and organizational levels when they feel emotionally exhausted. It has been documented that the most common forms of abusive behaviors encountered are unmanageable tasks and are being forced to work below the level of competence of employees (Chambers, McKee, Frampton, & Barclay, 2018). The abuse of supervisors, reckless and unjust behaviors compel subordinates to retaliate and engage in acts that are contrary to the legitimate objectives of the organization.

Retaliation is sometimes aimed at indirect sources due to variations in authority (such as between the manager and his employees), as a consequence of which co-workers are suffering. Consequently, counterproductive job behaviors accompanied by emotional exhaustion are detrimental to corporations as well as people operating in that organization. The employee thoughts become pre-occupied as they try to prevent or minimize the abuse, meaning they are unable to perform to a high standard (Ahmad, Athar, Azam, Hamstra, & Hanif, 2019). The employee's mindset is distracted as they try to avoid or mitigate the violence, which ensures that they cannot reach a high standard. Emotionally smart individuals, however, are more likely to control themselves to prevent wrongdoing. Because emotional intelligence requires knowing other people and thereby empathizing with the people around them, they are aware of the reasons for others' wrongdoing and can forgive them readily rather than taking revenge. Furthermore, emotionally smart people can manage swings in moods and do not get stuck in adverse feelings and are thus less likely to participate in counterproductive employment behaviors. It is hypothesized on the grounds of the above argument;

H5: The relationship between AS and CWB is moderated by EI such that lower the EI stronger will be the relationship and vice versa.

According to Mobley (1977), staff have the intention to leave after experiencing discontent and therefore ultimately leave the organization. According to him, a worker first evaluates the current job, analyzes the pleasure or discontent connected with the current job, then ponders to leave, evaluates the price of switching, tries to assess the options, effectively evaluates the options, compares them with the current job, thinks about quitting or staying and lastly stops or remains with the present company. Not only do emotionally smart staff have less intention of withdrawal, but they also assist others in reducing stress and frustration in their workplace. Wong et al. (2002) says that favorable work experience makes staff more organizationally engaged and reduces their desire to leave. Emotionally smart staff experience favorable emotions and are more satisfied with their positions. On the contrary, as per Carmeli (2003) experiences of more anger, discontent and depression among less emotionally smart staff are common. Emotions are strongly linked to the intention to quit, which leads to real turnover. Those with a high degree of emotional intelligence understand how to deal with challenging circumstances and adapt when needed to reduce their depression or wrath (Carmeli, 2003). It is therefore hypothesized on the basis of above literature;

H6: The relationship between AS and ITQ is moderated by EI such that lower the EI stronger will be the relationship and vice versa.

Conceptual Framework:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Methods

The study is cross-sectional since data were gathered at a single point of time. The research was performed in natural environment, where respondents could perform their work as normal and the interference of the researcher was minimal so the settings of the study were non-contrived. A very comprehensive 5 point Likert scale questionnaire was used to determine the effect of the abuse of managers. This study's population involves

adult staff (both males and females) employed in the banking sector in Punjab, Pakistan. Very few studies examining the detrimental impacts of abusive supervision in this industry of Pakistan have been carried out yet, to the best of the understanding of the researcher. Therefore 4 distinct banks were taken from Lahore, Pakistan. In addition, due to lengthy working hours in this industry, employees appear to be more emotionally exhausted and involved in deviant job behaviors and turnover intention. For sample size calculation, Klein's item response theory was used, which is formulated as $n = \frac{10}{r^2}$ (51*10). The investigator suggested a sample size of 510 people operating in banking sector of Lahore, Pakistan, according to this formula. In specific, non-probability sampling approach is used for this study. 510 questionnaires were sent online to staff employed in banking sector, 472 of which were completed and obtained. The effective response rate therefore amounts to 92.5%.

The research was conducted online using Google Docs. Two software have been used to analyze the information, i.e. AMOS 24 and SPSS 22. Some of the tests have been implemented on SPSS 22 including descriptive stats, normality and reliability. Other tests have been implemented on AMOS 24 including CFA (Confirmatory Factor Analysis) and tests for moderation. No missing values have been identified as data was collected in soft copy and every area was labelled required so no query was missed.

Results

4.1 Sample Composition

Table 1 illustrates the characteristic of the frequency of respondents with respect to demographics i.e. Age, Gender, Qualification and experience.

Table 1: Demographic Variables Analysis

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Gender	Male	368	78	78
	Female	104	22	22
Age	15-20	–	–	–
	21-25	165	35	35
	26-30	64	13.6	13.6
	31-35	161	34.1	34.1
	36-40	82	17.4	17.4
Qualification	Middle	–	–	–
	Matric	–	–	–
	Intermediate	–	–	–
	Bachelors	325	68.9	68.9
	Masters	147	31.1	31.1
Experience	0-5	293	62.1	62.1
	6-10	71	15	15
	11-15	64	13.6	13.6
	16-20	44	9.3	9.3

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 represents the values of mean and standard deviation. The mean values fall between 2.4 to 2.9 and standard deviation between 0.33 and 0.94.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	SD
AS	2.4674	0.94758
EI	3.355	0.33033
EE	2.7333	0.80099

CWB	2.6307	0.90456
ITQ	2.9887	0.85564

4.3 Data Reliability

The table below displays the Cronbach alpha values of the scale used in this investigation. Since all values are greater than 0.7 thereby very good to retain. The alpha value of "emotional intelligence" is 0.669, which is nearer to 0.7. An acceptable rule of thumb is that the 0.6-0.7 alpha value is acceptable, and 0.8 and higher is a good level. Nonetheless, values above 0.95 are not considered good as they might indicate redundancies (Hulin, Netemeyer, and Cudeck, 2001)

Table 3: Data Reliability

Variables	Cronbach Alpha
AS	0.924
EI	0.669
EE	0.868
CWB	0.901
ITQ	0.765

4.4 Structural Model and Model Fitness Indices

This research uses AMOS 24 to perform Structural Equation Modeling. This test allows us to determine the association between the measured variables and latent constructs, to name unobserved variables and to define the fitness of the model. Following the illustration of the route diagram we measure the outcomes, including thresholds for fitness models (CFI, GFI, AGFI, RMSEA, CMIN). The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) must be higher or equal to 0.90 according to Hu & Bentler (1999). The figure closer to 1 shows that it suits well. The Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) must surpass 0.9, for adequate fitness the Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) must be more than 0.85. The Root Mean Square Approximation Error (RMSEA) value should not exceed 0.08 Hu & Bentler (1999), and the Chi-square mean should be less than 3 and closer to 1 to retain.

Table 4: Model Fitness Indices

Model	Hypothesized	Thresholds
CMIN/DF	2.686	< 3
GFI	0.899	≥ 0.9
AGFI	0.876	≥ 0.85
CFI	0.94	≥ 0.9
RMSEA	0.053	< 0.08

The model is fit, as all indicator values fall within the expected range. CMIN/DF is lower than 3, GFI is nearer to 0.9, AGFI exceeds 0.85, the CFI crosses 0.9 and the RMSEA is below 0.08. Since all the values fall within required range so the model is fit. However, a few variables have been deleted to make a nice fit.

Figure 2: Structural Model

4.5 Path Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

The study has six hypotheses which have been tested through SEM and Regression. Table 4.4 demonstrates that Emotional Intelligence has an insignificant negative impact on Emotional Exhaustion with the value of -0.114. Abusive Supervision has a significant positive impact on CWB with the value of 0.3, thus **hypothesis 2** is accepted. Emotional intelligence has an insignificant negative impact on counterproductive work behaviors with the value of -0.067. Abusive supervision has a significant positive impact on emotional exhaustion with the value of 0.402, thus **hypothesis 1** is accepted. Similarly Abusive Supervision has a positive significant impact on Intention to Quit with the value of 0.333, thus **hypothesis 3** is accepted. Emotional intelligence has insignificant negative impact on intention to quit with the value of -0.04. Interaction term int_AS_EI, has an insignificant impact on intention to quit, counterproductive work behaviors and emotional exhaustion with the value of 0.007, 0.017 and -0.023 respectively. Hence no moderation found and **hypotheses 4, 5 and 6** are rejected.

Figure 3: Path Analysis
Table 5: Hypotheses Testing

		Estimate	P
ZEmotional_exhaustion	<--- ZEmotional_intel	-0.114	0.007
Zcounter_behaviours	<--- ZAbusive_Sup	0.3	***
Zintentiontoquit	<--- int_AS_EI	0.007	0.865
Zcounter_behaviours	<--- ZEmotional_intel	-0.067	0.126
ZEmotional_exhaustion	<--- ZAbusive_Sup	0.402	***
Zintentiontoquit	<--- ZAbusive_Sup	0.333	***

Zcounter_behaviours	<---	int_AS_EI	0.017	0.694
Zintentiontoquit	<---	ZEmotional_intel	-0.04	0.358
ZEmotional_exhaustion	<---	int_AS_EI	-0.023	0.582

4.6 Pearson Correlation

The table below shows the outcome of this study's correlation between observed factors.

Table 6: Pearson Correlation

		1	2	3	4	5
1.	AS	1				
2.	EI	.070	1			
3.	EE	.431**	-.103**	1		
4.	CWB	.325**	-.061	.524**	1	
5.	ITQ	.342**	-.051	.540**	.452**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table demonstrates that all independent variables (Emotional Exhaustion, Counterproductive work behaviors and Intention to Quit) are correlated with dependent variable (Abusive Supervision) with r values of .431, .325, and .342 and $p < 0.01$.

Limitations and Future Directions

In this research the investigator also noted a few limitations, as in past studies.

- Very few negative impacts of abusive supervision were examined in this research. The connection with several other factors, including the job performance, Citizenship Behaviour at workplace (OCB), commitment, dedication to work, etc. remained unnoticed.
- In addition, as information were obtained in a softcopy (through on-line surveys), some workers might not be aware of the issue to the truest extent so the outcomes could be damaged. It is recommended to future researchers to gather the data in hard form in their personal supervision while clarifying the context and ensure the understand ability of the respondents.
- The current study has taken account the cross-sectional design for collection of data. The reason of this research design is mainly due to lack of time. However, the results of the research could have been impacted. Longitudinal research, however, can be more efficient and findings can be different.
- Only one variable's moderating influence i.e. emotional intelligence has been considered but many other factors (e.g. tenacity of employees and the absence of corporate engagement) can still be observed to distinguish between abusive supervision and consequences.
- Some staff possibly may find some questions too private that they have neutralized their answers owing to their awareness and certain other workplace limitations.
- This research was only performed in Lahore, Pakistan, and information gathered only from single city was used to interpret the outcomes. Cross-cultural research can give a deeper understanding of these relations.
- Emotional intelligence can also be examined as a mediator among the proposed relationships. Similarly many other situational factors can be used as mediators or moderators while investigating the impact of abusive supervision on job outcomes and other deviant behaviors.
- Daily fluctuations e.g. workload, lack of sleep etc. and short term experiences may also influence the responses of candidates which are not considered in this study. Future scholars should also consider these factors in their study and should ask for responses based on more than six months' experience.

Research Implications

The findings of direct relationships in this study, comply with the literature and indicate that abusive behavior of supervisor lead to EE, CWB and ITQ of workforce. The research specifies that strict mechanisms such as organizational control and the legal systems should be used to eliminate negative consequences of abusive supervisory behavior. And in order to ensure the retention of management roles, companies must closely monitor the actions of managers who are involved in aggressive and abusive actions against subordinates. In addition, the training sessions should be carried out at the management stage, to encourage the managers to improve their attitudes and behaviors, so that stress can be minimized and a healthier atmosphere is established. Secondly, a leader needs to be a role model for leading workers ethically. And the relationship between the coercive supervision and deviant conduct is bidirectional, according to the latest findings and historical facts. For this reason, the organization should define successful ways and clear guidelines to cope with employee deviation. Ethical leading behavior, for example, allows the company to enforce an ethical code of conduct and handle employee actions morally. The objective of this study was not only to investigate the negative

consequences of abusive behavior of managers but also to examine the influence of emotional intelligence as a moderator. Emotional intelligence has in fact been used as a moderator between AS and ITQ, this study also examined its moderating role with other two relationships. In Pakistani context, we attained that employees respond negatively towards the organization and its employees when they experience abusive behavior irrespective of emotional intelligence. In certain ways both theories also indicate that workers at work do not only reciprocate positive or negative actions but also share resources that affect a whole organization. Our study findings also practically imply that organizations should analyze the causes for supervisory maltreatment and focus on HR policies for example, to devise strategies that reduce interpersonal mistreatment and stress.

Conclusion

This research focuses on examining the negative repercussions of abusive supervision and how it influences an employee's emotional exhaustion, their involvement in deviant behaviors both at individual and organizational level, also their intent to leave the organization, with the moderating effect of emotional intelligence. However, researcher found that abusive behavior of supervisor correlates directly with emotional exhaustion, deviant job behaviors, and intention of quitting the job, but the results of this research do not support moderation between the said variables. Since the findings show the acceptance of direct relationships in Pakistani context so it is recommended to future scholars to conduct a research aimed to eradicate the negative behaviors of supervisors. It is also concluded on the basis of findings that workers believe the managers as an agent of the organization and think that they follow the instructions of upper management. Hence, when they receive something negative, employees also reciprocate with negative behaviors by involving in deviant workplace behaviors. However, the results of our study also indicate that emotional intelligence is neither strengthening nor weakening the proposed relationships in Pakistani banking sector, but the results may vary in other sectors or even in other cultures.

References

- Ahmad, J., Athar, M. R., Azam, R. I., Hamstra, M. R., & Hanif, M. (2019). A resource perspective on abusive supervision and extra-role behaviors: The role of subordinates' psychological capital. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 26(1), 73-86.
- Ahmad, J., Athar, M. R., Azam, R. I., Hamstra, M. R., & Hanif, M. (2019). A resource perspective on abusive supervision and extra-role behaviors: The role of subordinates' psychological capital. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 26(1), 73-86.
- Asghar, M., & Ahmad, Z. (2017). Impact of Abusive supervision on workplace deviance behavior; Role of international justice. *Current Economics and Management Research*, 3(1), 1-11.
- Ashforth, B. (1994). Petty tyranny in organizations. *Human relations*, 47(7), 755-778.
- Blau, P. M. (1964). *Exchange and power in social life*. New York, NY: Wiley and Sons.
- Cropanzano, R. & Mitchell, M.S. (2005). Social exchange theory: An interdisciplinary review. *Journal of Management*, 31(6), 874-900 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0149206305279602>
- Bruk-Lee, V., Khoury, H. A., Nixon, A. E., Goh, A., & Spector, P. E. (2009). Replicating and extending past personality/job satisfaction meta-analyses. *Human Performance*, 22(2), 156-189.
- Carmeli A (2003) The relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitudes, behavior and outcomes: An examination among senior managers. *Journal of Managerial Psychology* 18: 788-813.
- Chambers, C. N., Frampton, C. M., McKee, M., & Barclay, M. (2018). 'It feels like being trapped in an abusive relationship': Bullying prevalence and consequences in the New Zealand senior medical workforce: A cross-sectional study. *BMJ open*, 8(3), 1-10. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2017-020158
- Choi, W., Kim, S. L., & Yun, S. (2018). A Social Exchange Perspective of Abusive Supervision and Knowledge Sharing: Investigating the Moderating Effects of Psychological Contract Fulfillment and Self-Enhancement Motive. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 34(3), 305-309.
- Ciulla, J. B. (1999). The importance of leadership in shaping business values. *Long Range Planning*, 32(2), 166-177.
- Cropanzano, R., Howes, J. C., Grandey, A. A., & Toth, P. (1997). The relationship of organizational politics and support to work behaviors, attitudes, and stress. *Journal of Organizational behavior*, 159-180.
- Emerson, R. M. (1976). Social exchange theory. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 2: 335-362 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1146/annurev.so.02.080176.002003>
- ForsBrandebo, M., Österberg, J., & Berglund, A. K. (2019). The impact of constructive and destructive leadership on soldier's job satisfaction. *Psychological Reports*, 122(3), 1068-1086. doi:10.1177/0033294118771542
- Fox, E., Russo, R., Bowles, R., & Dutton, K. (2001). Do threatening stimuli draw or hold visual attention in subclinical anxiety? *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 130(4), 681.
- Gkorezis, P. (2015). Supervisor support and pro-environmental behavior: the mediating role of LMX. *Management Decision*, 53(5), 1045-1060.

- Gouldner, A. W. (1960). The norm of reciprocity: A preliminary statement. *American sociological review*, 161-178.
- Hamid, A. R., Juhdi, H. N., Ismail, A. N., & Abdullah, A. N. (2015). Abusive supervision and workplace deviance as moderated by spiritual intelligence: An empirical study of Selangor employees. *Malaysian Journal of Society and Space*, 12(2), 191-202.
- Hu, L. & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling*, 6(1), 1-5
- Hulin, C., Netemeyer, R., and Cudeck, R. (2001). Can a Reliability Coefficient Be Too High? *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, Vol. 10, Nr. 1, 55-58
- Hussain, I., & Sia, S. K. (2017). Power Distance Orientation Dilutes the Effect of Abusive Supervision on Workplace Deviance. *Management and Labour Studies*, 42(4), 293-305.
- Inness, M., Barling, J., & Turner, N. (2005). Understanding supervisor-targeted aggression: A within-person, between-jobs design. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 90(4), 731.
- Judge, T. A., Piccolo, R. F., & Ilies, R. (2004). The forgotten ones? The validity of consideration and initiating structure in leadership research. *Journal of applied psychology*, 89(1), 36.
- Kelloway, E. K., & Barling, J. (2010). Leadership development as an intervention in occupational health psychology. *Work & Stress*, 24(3), 260-279.
- Liden, R.C., Graen, G., 1980. Generalizability of the vertical dyad linkage model of leadership. *Academy of Management Journal* 23, 451-465.
- Liden, R.C., Maslyn, J.M., 1998. Multidimensionality of leader-member exchange: an empirical assessment through scale development. *Journal of Management* 24, 43-72.
- Liu, X.; Yu, K. Emotional stability and citizenship fatigue: The role of emotional exhaustion and job stressors. *Personal. Individ. Differ.* 2019, 139, 254-262
- Marcus-Newhall, A., Pedersen, W. C., Carlson, M., & Miller, N. (2000). Displaced aggression is alive and well: a meta-analytic review. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 78(4), 670.
- Maslach C & Goldberg J (1998) Prevention of burnout: new perspectives. *Applied and Preventative Psychology* 7, 63-74
- Maslach C & Jackson SE (1986) *Maslach Burnout Inventory*, 2nd edn. Consulting Psychologist Press, Palo Alto, CA.
- Maslach C (1982) *Burnout: The Cost of Caring*. Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ.
- Maslach, C., Schaufeli, W. B., & Leiter, M. P. (2001). Job burnout. *Annual review of psychology*, 52(1), 397-422.
- Middlemiss, S. (2011). The psychological contract and implied contractual terms: Synchronous or asynchronous models? *International Journal of Law and Management*, 53(1), 32-50. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17542431111111872>
- Mikolajczak M, Menil C & Luminet O (2007) Explaining the protective effect of emotional trait intelligence regarding occupational stress: exploration of emotional labour processes. *Journal of Research in Personality* 41, 1107-1117.
- Mobley William H (1977) Intermediate linkages in the relationship between job satisfaction and employee turnover. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 62: 237-240.
- Mobley, W. H., Horner, S. O., & Hollingsworth, A. T. (1978). An evaluation of precursors of hospital employee turnover. *Journal of Applied psychology*, 63(4), 408.
- Netemeyer, R. G., Brashear-Alejandro, T., & Boles, J. S. (2004). A cross-national model of job-related outcomes of work role and family role variables: A retail sales context. *Journal of the Academy of marketing Science*, 32(1), 49-60.
- Nikolova, I.; van Dam, K.; Van Ruysseveldt, J.; De Witte, H. Feeling Weary? Feeling Insecure? Are All Workplace Changes Bad News? *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2019, 16, 1842.
- Northouse, P. G. (2018). *Leadership: Theory and practice*: Sage publications.
- O'Boyle Jr, E. H., Pollack, J. M., & Rutherford, M. W. (2012). Exploring the relation between family involvement and firms' financial performance: A meta-analysis of main and moderator effects. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 27(1), 1-18.
- Paulhus, D. L., & Williams, K. M. (2002). The dark triad of personality: Narcissism, Machiavellianism, and psychopathy. *Journal of research in personality*, 36(6), 556-563.
- Pradhan, S. and Jena, L. K. (2016), "The Moderating Role of Neutralizers on the Relationship between Abusive Supervision and Intention to Quit: A Proposed Model", *Journal of Human Values*, Vol. 22, No. 3, pp. 238-248.
- Raabe, B., & Beehr, T. A. (2003). Formal mentoring versus supervisor and coworker relationships: Differences in perceptions and impact. *Journal of organizational behavior*, 24(3), 271-293.

- Robinson, S. L., & Bennett, R. J. (1995). A typology of deviant workplace behaviors: A multidimensional scaling study. *Academy of management journal*, 38(2), 555-572.
- Rousseau, D. M. (1989). Psychological and implied contracts in organizations. *Employee Responsibilities and Rights Journal*, 2(2), 121-139. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF01384942>
- Rousseau, D. M. (1995). *Psychological contracts in organizations: Understanding written and unwritten agreements*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Salovey, P. and Mayer, J.D. (1990), "Emotional intelligence", *Imagination, Cognition and Personality* Vol. 9 No. 3, pp. 185-211.
- Schaufeli WB & Enzmann D (1998) *The Burnout Companion to Study and Practice: A Critical Analysis*. Taylor & Francis, London.
- Schmid, E. A., PircherVerdorfer, A., & Peus, C. V. (2018). Different shades—different effects? Consequences of different types of destructive leadership. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 1289.
- Spector, P. E. (1997). *Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes, and consequences* (Vol. 3): Sage publications.
- Tepper, B. J., Duffy, M. K. and Shaw, J. D. (2001), "Personality moderators of the relationship between abusive supervision and subordinates' resistance", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 86, No. 5, pp. 974–983.
- Tepper, B.J., Duffy, M.K., Henle, C.A. and Lambert, L.S. (2006), "Procedural injustice, victim precipitation, and abusive supervision", *Personnel Psychology*, Vol. 59 No. 1, pp. 101-123.
- Uhl-Bien, M., & Maslyn, J. (2003). Reciprocity in manager-subordinate relationships: Components, configurations, and outcomes. *Journal of Management*, 29, 511-532. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2063_03_00023-0
- Valentine, S., & Barnett, T. (2003). Ethics code awareness, perceived ethical values, and organizational commitment. *Journal of personal selling & Sales Management*, 23(4), 359-367.
- Van Hootegeem, A.; De Witte, H. Qualitative Job Insecurity and Informal Learning: A Longitudinal Test of Occupational Self-Efficacy and Psychological Contract Breach as Mediators. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2019, 16, 1847.
- Whitman, M. V., Halbesleben, J. R., & Holmes IV, O. (2014). Abusive Supervision and Feedback Avoidance: the Mediating Role of Emotional Exhaustion. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 35(1), 38-53.
- Wong CS, Law KS (2002) The effects of leader and follower emotional intelligence on performance and attitude: An exploratory study. *The Leadership Quarterly* 13: 243-274.
- Wright, T. A., & Cropanzano, R. (1998). Emotional exhaustion as a predictor of job performance and voluntary turnover. *Journal of applied psychology*, 83(3), 486.
- Yang, J., Mossholder, K. W., & Peng, T. (2009). Supervisory procedural justice effects: The mediating roles of cognitive and affective trust. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 20(2), 143-154.
- Zhang, Y.; Liu, X.; Xu, S.; Yang, L.Q.; Bednall, T.C. Why abusive supervision impacts employee OCB and CWB: A meta-analytic review of competing mediating mechanisms. *J. Manag.* 2019.

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